

I-CLAIM

**Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe**

Irregular migrants in the Dutch Domestic Work Sector

Sector report

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Executive Summary

Domestic work is a sector that offers employment to many irregular migrants in the Netherlands. As migrants cannot legally work without a residence permit, their options are mostly limited to sectors such as cleaning, construction, or delivery. Domestic work is one of the least regulated sectors due to the *Regeling Dienstverlening aan Huis*, which exempts private employers from many formal obligations if they employ someone for less than four days a week. This deregulation has created a legal grey area where many employers are unclear about their responsibilities.

Domestic work is, therefore, a common job sector for irregular migrants in the Netherlands. Interviews with workers in Utrecht reveal a variety of paths into the sector. Some arrived planning to work in domestic jobs, while others turned to cleaning after losing legal status or when their asylum claims were rejected. Workers vary in how central domestic work is to their livelihoods; some have ten clients and earn around €15-€18 per hour, while others work sporadically and may live in shelters. Jobs are typically found through informal networks, especially strong among Brazilian, Filipino, and Indonesian communities.

The employer-employee relationship between domestic workers and their employers is largely shaped by trust and physical absence. Most cleaners work while employers are away, using keys or hidden entry methods, and are paid informally. Trust, often based on referrals, is a central component of this system. Nevertheless, sometimes, personal bonds formed with those employers who were home. However, these blurred lines between work and friendship sometimes also complicate negotiations about pay and workload, which, in general, were difficult to negotiate. Irregular status limits workers' ability to negotiate even more.

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1. Introduction

This study aims to explore the complexities of irregularity within the domestic work sector in the Netherlands. It examines the everyday realities of irregular migrant domestic workers, drawing on interviews with workers in Utrecht. Domestic work in the Netherlands is one of the least regulated employment sectors in the Netherlands, particularly due to the: *Regeling Dienstverlening aan Huis*, the Dutch domestic work policy which creates an ambiguous legal environment that facilitates informal employment. This, however, also creates employment opportunities for those formally excluded from the labour market, such as irregular migrants.

Based on 22 interviews with irregular migrants working as domestic workers in Utrecht, the analysis highlights how irregular status intersects with working conditions, employer relations, and strategies for survival, while also shedding light on the role of migrant networks, informal support systems, and collective organising in navigating life and labour without legal status. The report will highlight how the informal organisation of the domestic work market opens doors for irregular migrants. This market mainly relies on word-of-mouth referrals, where trust and reputation are essential. Additionally, it will discuss how many irregular migrants start domestic work by assisting more experienced workers, using that experience as a gateway into the field.

2. Methodology

This report is based on interviews with 22 irregular migrant domestic workers, including one object-based follow-up interview, and eight stakeholders. The domestic workers originally came from a wide variety of countries, such as: Afghanistan, Armenia, Brazil, Colombia, Eritrea, Iran, Nigeria, the Philippines. The interviews were collected in Utrecht over six months, from December 2024 to April 2025. Most interviews lasted an hour and took place in people's homes or semi-public spaces. Most interviews were conducted in English, Dutch and Portuguese. A Nigerian, a Brazilian, and a Dutch community researcher were hired on the project to support data collection. They facilitated contact with participants and made it possible to do interviews in people's native language. The involvement of community researchers was crucial to reach potential participants through their networks, but also in building trust and creating a more comfortable interview setting. Moreover, they contributed additional layers of contextual and cultural understanding, helping to interpret experiences, themes and dynamics that came up in the interviews. All interviewees consented to having their interviews recorded. As a form of remuneration for their participation, the migrant workers received a €15 voucher for a local supermarket. Pseudonyms are used throughout the report. Forms of AI, i.e., Grammarly and ChatGPT, have been used in the copyediting of this report.

In the Netherlands, the irregularity found in the domestic work sector pertains to both the migration status of the workers and their employment. Those interviewed for this research either had no legal migration status at the time or spoke about periods during which they were without a residence permit. This includes visa overstayers, rejected asylum seekers, and individuals with a Dublin claim in the waiting period before they can reapply for asylum in the Netherlands. Some respondents, all from Brazil but not all Brazilian respondents, held residence permits in Portugal, and some were in the process of obtaining Portuguese citizenship. However, a Portuguese residence permit does not allow for work or extended stays in the Netherlands beyond 90 days.

3. Context: Domestic work in the Netherlands

In 2014, the market for direct domestic work in the Netherlands, excluding services provided by companies, was estimated to involve around 1 million households outsourcing some form of domestic work. This amounted to approximately 272 million hours of work per year. The total value of the domestic work market was estimated at 2.5 billion euros annually (Panteia, 2014). According to research by the Dutch Social Economic Council, 21.4 per cent of Dutch households indicate that they regularly pay someone to perform domestic work tasks for them, which includes all forms of domestic work, such as cleaning, gardening, home improvements, childcare, care for older people, and persons with disabilities. Moreover, the council anticipates an increase in demand for domestic work in the coming years, driven by the ageing population and the growing number of dual-income families (SER 2020: 25, 26).

The Netherlands, like some other northern European countries, has largely overlooked the need for migrant domestic workers, and domestic work is largely absent from migration policies (Lutz, 2016). Moreover, migrants are often not explicitly included in policies regulating domestic work, nor are there numbers of (irregular) migrants working in domestic work in the Netherlands mentioned in the studies evaluating the Dutch policy. The mostly qualitative studies on domestic work in the Netherlands do show a trend towards more migrants performing domestic work, especially in larger cities. However, these are not necessarily irregular migrants (see, for instance, Walsum, 2011; Botman, 2010; De Kort & Bakker, 2024, Marchetti, 2016).

Domestic work in the Netherlands primarily refers to cleaning, the vast majority of respondents were cleaners. Some respondents were also involved in care work, mainly childcare. The Dutch translation 'huishoudelijk werk' can be used as a synonym for cleaning; likewise, 'het huishouden doen' - which literally means 'doing the housework' or 'domestic work' - broadly refers to cleaning the house. While care work, childcare, or garden work, formally fall under domestic work, is mostly referred to by their respective terms. Domestic work colloquially refers to cleaning.

The *Regeling Dienstverlening aan huis* is the policy regulating domestic work in the Netherlands. It aims to encourage the employment of domestic workers by alleviating the administrative burden and financial risks associated with being an employer; essentially, it deregulates the sector.

It consists of a number of exceptions to regulations that apply to other (non-private) employers. The most significant exemption is that employers are not required to declare domestic work unless they hire someone for four days a week or more. The employer can, therefore, regularly pay someone, in cash or otherwise, without a contract. For domestic work to be entirely regular, the employee must declare the work to tax and employment authorities. It is widely known that domestic workers do not do this. However, even when fully regular employees who fall under this regulation are not insured for unemployment benefits and disability through the standard mandatory social insurance, they do not build up a pension through their employer. In case of illness, they are entitled to six weeks of salary instead of the standard two years. Yet, only a very small proportion of employers (5%) appear to be well-informed about the applicable laws and regulations. While more than half say they find it (very) important to comply with the rules, ultimately only 3.2 percent actually comply with all the rules (SER, 2020, p. 33). This creates a confusing situation between regular and irregular employment. Employers do not need to register employing a domestic worker. Yet, many employers are not aware of the rules. This creates a situation in which the employment is not irregular from the employer's side, but the employer thinks it is. Officially, the employment becomes irregular if the employee does not register their employment, yet there are few incentives to do so. Irregular migrants are

not allowed to work in the Netherlands and (Hajer et al. 2024), therefore, cannot register their employment, even if they wish to do so. Nor they are entitled to apply for a residence permit for any type of work. While the work of irregular migrant domestic workers is informal due to their formal exclusion from the labour market, under Dutch labour law, the rights outlined in the *Regeling dienstverlening aan huis* apply to everyone, including irregular migrants.

The Netherlands has not ratified ILO Convention 189 but continues to uphold the *Regeling Dienstverlening aan huis*. According to the advisory committee that assessed the possibility of ratification, the Convention primarily aims to combat abuse and exploitation, practices the committee claims are rare within the Netherlands. However, the committee does acknowledge a key shortcoming: the *Regeling Dienstverlening aan huis* does not afford domestic workers the same rights and protections as those granted to other workers, thereby falling short of the principle of equal treatment (Commissie Dienstverlening aan huis, 2014).

4. Domestic work in Utrecht

4.1. Irregularity and Domestic Work in the Netherlands

With this deregulated and confusing framework, in combination with the common practice of hiring workers in private households, domestic work is a common occupation for irregular migrants in the Netherlands (see also Walsum, 2011: 155). Consequently, this field is not confined to a single group of irregular migrants; the demographics of irregular domestic workers are pretty varied. While the image of domestic workers is often associated with females, many male irregular migrants also find employment in this sector, particularly in cleaning tasks. Moreover, in the interviews with delivery workers, we found that quite some delivery workers had also done domestic work at some point.

What I had to do was look for the Brazilian community that was here and adapt to the life of a person who is, who is, who is undocumented. So there are very few options: you're going to work on construction, you're going to work as a cleaner and you're going to work as a nanny or as a delivery person, which today is much more difficult because it's through the app. (Renata, Brazil)

A significant impact of being in an irregular migration status is that it often pushes individuals into domestic work. Lacking legal status prevents them from being formally employed, leaving a few sectors, such as domestic work, open to informal employment opportunities. Some migrants arrive already with the intention of working in domestic roles once they learn about the potential earnings, even without legal residence. In contrast, others may turn to this work after losing their legal status, such as following a failed asylum application. Domestic work is often viewed as a reasonably decent job. Although the majority of respondents expressed a good level of contentment with their jobs, they indicated a strong preference for switching to regular employment if they were to acquire a residence permit. In the Dutch landscape, domestic work does not serve as a pathway to regularising one's stay. Employment in any sector generally does not lead to regularisation, as noted in the I-LCIAM WP3 report (Hajer et al. 2024).

4.2. Who are irregular domestic workers in Utrecht?

The domestic workers interviewed in Utrecht can be roughly divided into two types: those who had domestic work as their main employment and had multiple cleaning addresses a week, through which they managed to provide for themselves and, at times, their families. In terms of numbers, this means 10 addresses a week, for a going rate of approximately 15-18 euros an hour. The second type, which engages in domestic work

sporadically, such as when asked by friends or acquaintances, or has just a few cleaning clients each week. This latter profile was commonly found among those residing in shelter programs. While live-in domestic workers are relatively uncommon in the Netherlands, one of the interviewees lived with their employer at the time of the interview, and one other indicated that they had lived with an employer in the past. Moreover, while speaking with delivery workers, several shared that they had previous experience in domestic work.

4.3. How do domestic workers find work?

Respondents reported various methods for finding work in the domestic sector. Most found work through contacts they already had. This occurred, for example, within their co-national community. Certain nationalities, particularly Indonesians, Filipinos, and Brazilians, have established strong networks within the domestic work sector to help their fellow countrypeople find jobs. Finding these addresses to clean occurs in different ways, among which through co-national community networks, WhatsApp groups and Facebook groups. Finding work also occurred through contact with employers they already knew who were looking for domestic workers or through civil society networks such as churches. Some respondents reported using apps and websites to find cleaning addresses. For example, within Facebook groups or WhatsApp groups of migrant communities exchanging information and work opportunities, these were not specifically related to domestic work. While there are some online platforms specifically designed to cater to the demand and offer of domestic work, these were not utilised. One respondent regularly advertises herself on Marktplaats.nl (an online marketplace mostly for second-hand things). Another prevalent method involved purchasing 'addresses' from established domestic workers, essentially taking over their clients for a fee akin to a few weeks' wages. Sometimes, finding a cleaning address even began before arriving in the Netherlands; for example, people from the Philippines came to the Netherlands on a tourist or au-pair visa, intending to overstay and work as a domestic worker. Some addresses were pre-arranged before arrival, often by family members. Another example is the recruitment of Brazilian domestic workers from Portugal to work as domestic workers in the Netherlands.

4.3.1. *Entering domestic work as a 'helper.'*

An interesting example of entering the market for domestic workers is what occurred within the Brazilian community. Here, many newcomers began their work by working alongside another domestic worker, taking on the role of a 'helper'. This entry point could stem from family ties, such as a brother who had already settled in the Netherlands, or from connections made through Facebook or WhatsApp among Brazilians in the Netherlands, specifically in Utrecht. Helpers typically accompanied more seasoned workers to cleaning jobs, with the earnings split between them. This division was sometimes equal, or at 40/60, but sometimes unequal, with reports of helpers earning as little as €5 an hour.

For four months, I lived with her and worked with her; we did the cleaning. (...) She was very straightforward, she paid like that. She'd divide it up, like, if it was a house for €20 an hour, we'd do the house in four hours, but we'd each get 40. (Fernanda, Brazil)

The person facilitating this entry into domestic work often acted as a blend of coworker and employer. Though live-in domestic work was uncommon in the Netherlands, it was not unusual for newcomers to temporarily reside with the domestic worker who brought them in. These dynamics highlight a system of mutual dependency, where new domestic workers heavily relied not only on their employers but also, at

times, on their intermediaries within the migrant community for access to work, housing, and crucial information. While these relationships could offer support, they also left room for exploitation. For instance, one woman suffered a leg injury in a bicycle accident while working as a helper. The person she was working with subsequently pressured her to keep working despite her pain, and she was misled into thinking that undocumented individuals could not go to the hospital.

4.4. Relationship with employers: when the employers are away

The relationship with employers is an interesting one, as the vast majority of domestic workers rarely see them. Domestic workers often carry keychains full of keys to let themselves into the homes of all their various employers. Sometimes, they let themselves in with a key they find under a doormat or flowerpot. Payment often occurs 'on the table', where employers leave cash on the kitchen counter or dining table. Alternatively, if the worker has a bank account, employers can pay with a bank transfer or a so-called 'Tikkie', a money-transfer app.

Most of the houses I work in hardly ever have anyone at home, so I see very little of them. I have the keys to the house and we book on days when no-one will be home so that I'm free to work. (Camila, Brazil)

90% We have the keys. It's really nice because they trust us and we have a key. The ones we don't have a key are because they work from home, they're always at home. When they're not at home, there's the trick of hiding the key under the carpet, behind the plant. Then we have access to the house. (Letícia, Brazil)

While this kind of employment may seem impersonal, some employers leave little gestures for the worker, personalising the relationship even when they do not see each other. Respondents, for instance, shared how employers would leave coffee and tea ready for them to use in the kitchen and ask for small gestures. Moreover, the nature of domestic work makes the employment relationship very intimate, even when the employers are not present. Domestic workers enter all spheres of the private home; they enter the bedrooms, clean the sheets off the bed, and do the washing, all tasks they describe as very intimate.

trust is also important. How do I know? Because we're inside people's intimacies? (...)

Generally, people enter to the living room to the garden. We go into the bathroom, we go into the dressing room, we go into the bedroom, we go into intimacy. Like it or not, we know what's going on in people's homes. (Renata, Brazil)

Moreover, having the keys that grant access to the private home, even when the employer is not present, is a process that requires a great deal of trust. However, this trust often did not derive from a strong personal relationship between employer and employee. Respondents, therefore, emphasised the importance of referrals and reputation in gaining this trust and viewed it as a significant responsibility not to betray the trust.

There are people who, on the first day of the interview, already give us the key because they are all referrals. So the clients refer us, "they have already referred themselves; they are trustworthy." (Letícia, Brazil)

4.5. Relationship with employer: When the employers are at home

The majority of employers were not at home when the domestic workers worked in their houses. When employers were at home, domestic workers indicated that they have relatively good relationships with their employers, sometimes referring to them in very familiar ways. For example, a respondent who, while speaking about her favourite employer, referred to an elderly employer, asked her granny and shared with us how much she liked chatting with her while cleaning her room in a nursing home. Having a good relationship with an employer is beneficial for domestic workers (see also, for instance, Marchetti 2016). In general, many domestic workers obtained new addresses to clean via their employers, who referred them to neighbours, friends, and family members. But good contact with employers can also help in finding support in other ways, both moral and practical.

so the first the first woman, I thought she was sick, so she was staying at home as I was cleaning. So we get to talk. She also helped me find, like, most of the jobs she helped. So. Well, I was really close with her. I don't work for her now, but I kind of miss her. (Haben, Eritrea)

However, having a close relationship with the employer can also blur the boundaries between work and friendship on both sides. For example, talking and drinking coffee and discussing their lives with employers during work hours takes time away from the domestic worker that they could have spent cleaning, as they are often not paid for chatting. However, addressing this can be challenging and may lead to tensions in the relationship. One respondent (Ranata from Brazil) shared about how an employer had become a friend, yet indicated how this made it more difficult to talk about the working conditions. Stated that the employer might have forgotten that she was there to work and not as a friend, making it more challenging to ask for more pay or fewer tasks in the time she was there to clean the house.

4.6. Negotiating working conditions

Being irregular can make it challenging to negotiate working conditions. Many of the respondents did not engage in extensive negotiations with their employers; instead, they would increase the hourly rate of cleaning services for new cleaning addresses. In some instances attempts at negotiating have negative effects.

We had this campaign two years ago, for vakantiegeld [holiday pay]. We formulated a letter for the employers and. Yeah, the members they gave to the employers, some were like okay, okay. But in one case, one of the employers, uh, fired her. Representative of the migrant domestic workers union

However, some domestic workers approached the negotiation with a more entrepreneurial spirit. Notably, these were often people who were more secure in their living situation, and were not as dependent on a particular cleaning address for their livelihood. For example, Renata established an informal cleaning business.

I always do an interview before I start working for someone. During this interview, I make it very clear that we work by the hour, that we work in pairs and that it won't always be the same people going to clean their house. (...) so there's going to be a turnover, but the quality is going to be the same. And so, there's a negotiation at the beginning and the client, depending on what the client needs, and I'll set the price

Later in the interview, she added:

Clean it yourself. Now, if you don't want to clean, if you don't want to, you have to pay. It's expensive, it's an expensive service. So it's something else. I have it, thank God, even though I'm not regular in the country, I have a name here, I am respected. So, a lot of people come to me every day, I get messages from people wanting me to work for them, not to be arrogant, that is just the truth. (Renata, Brazil)

One of the most challenging aspects of negotiating working conditions in domestic work is the persistent idea of 'no work, no pay'. This means that if the domestic worker has not worked, either because they were unable to work due to illness, for instance, or because the employer cancelled or requested that the domestic worker not come in for a period of time, the domestic worker will not receive a salary.

If it's holiday. Yeah. And the employers, they said don't work because we are on holiday, so they don't allow because the house is still clean. So that is six weeks without us. So if you are not working then no pay. (Gloria, Philippines)

Yeah, because if you are like, sick, you don't get money. You know, if you're undocumented or if they cancel one day, then you don't get money. I had this also like they cancelled last moment. So you don't get money, you don't get paid, but you can't earn it. I, I had to fight with one of them not to reapply, but she cancelled the last moment. "My daughter has an exam today up there. And if you come to clean, then she cannot focus." It's such a weird excuse. She was always at home. I could clean down and said she could stay in her room. Or I could go upstairs. She could say, I'm sorry. This is not good because I count money, and it's my weekly money. I need it, and you cancel the last moment. Then she stopped working with me. She was like, no, thank you. I don't want to work with you anymore at all. (Neda, Iran)

The severity of this situation became especially apparent during the COVID-19 pandemic and the subsequent lockdown periods. This was a period in which many irregular domestic workers who had been managing their irregular situation quite well working as domestic workers got into real trouble. As they were not able to work and subsequently did not receive our salaries, they could not pay their rent, lost their housing, and became homeless in the middle of lockdown. Yet, much to the surprise of domestic workers themselves, there were also notable exceptions to the 'no work, no pay'.

So, I can't explain how it happened, but I kept getting paid. During the pandemic, all the houses I worked in kept paying me, and most of them couldn't pay the full amount. So, they were like: 'I'll pay you half to stay at home. (Camila, Brazil)

Moreover, during the COVID lockdown, there has been a campaign on the situation of domestic workers, as 'no work, no pay' was also an issue for Dutch domestic workers. This campaign highlighted the substandard work regulations for domestic workers.¹ While common, 'no work, no pay' is not legal. Under the Home Services Act, domestic workers are entitled to paid sick leave and vacation days. Moreover, under Dutch

¹ <https://www.fnv.nl/nieuwsbericht/algemeen-nieuws/2020/04/help-onze-huishoudelijk-werkers>

labour law, employers need to continue to pay their domestic workers when they cancel the cleaning. These employment rights also apply to irregular migrants.

*If the employee is available for work but cannot work due to a cause that is part of the employer's risk, for example, if there is no work available, the employer must continue paying the worker.
Written response of legal expert*

4.7. Effects of irregularity at work

Irregularity always played a role in the lives of respondents, also at work. Irregularity increases dependency on work to survive. As life in irregular conditions in the Netherlands means exclusion from almost all provisions and services, irregular migrants constrict their lives in many irregular ways. Therefore, they often depend on informal housing, such as subletting rooms or apartments, without any renter protection. In this case, losing work results in being unable to pay rent and, ultimately, losing their house (Hajer et al., 2025). Moreover, domestic workers indicated that being in an irregular situation can be a source of stress at work. Especially if employers know the workers are irregular, workers can fear that employers will use it against them or will report them to authorities, even if they do not do so.

*They know [that I do not have documents] but this is also a bit, uh, stressful because you think all the time if they call IND, police or whatever. But because of that, I went to the people that I know. I was like, I want to be sure that you know that person. Yeah. And they know my situation.
(Neda, Iran)*

However, their irregular situation can also be a source of stress if the employers are not aware of their situation. Many workers shared that they would not tell their employers about their irregular status, and their employers never ask. As described above, employers are exempted from registering the employment a domestic worker this makes it possible for migration status to never come up in the hiring process. However, for the domestic worker, mundane questions in everyday conversation can be a, sometimes painful, reminder of their irregular situation, as one respondent shared:

If someone does not know you always have to act, I cannot really talk, I have to pretend (...) and you know there will be questions like about holidays. They asked me where will you go on holiday with the kids. I say nothing. Because all these years I have not been on holiday (Nare, Armenia)

4.8. Effect of irregularity on everyday life

Housing insecurity loomed large for nearly all the domestic workers I spoke with, primarily due to their irregular migration status, which complicates the process of securing formal housing. This situation forced many to rely on informal arrangements, such as subletting rooms or apartments. Such precarious living situations often resulted in frequent relocations, heightened risks of scams, and noticeably high rent costs. While everyone faced their share of challenges, their experiences differed widely: some struggled to pay rents soaring as high as €2000, while others found themselves experiencing homelessness, sleeping on the streets of Utrecht. The majority reported being able to tap into various forms of support. Some were part of the LVV shelter program, a national initiative that's locally executed in Utrecht through a collaboration between the municipality and NGOs. This program offers shelter, legal and personal guidance, pocket money, and access to multiple services. Although these facilities provided a bed, their future remains

uncertain due to the current political climate. For those outside this initiative, support primarily came from NGOs and civil society, as they are largely excluded from most public social services in the Netherlands.

Many were aware of how to access medical care, whether independently or with assistance from organisations. Médecins du Monde was frequently mentioned for its clinics and walk-in hours. At the same time, STIL, a local NGO in Utrecht, stood out as a vital resource for medical access, legal advice, general guidance, and sometimes even financial aid. Alongside these formal resources, many leaned on informal support networks, with various churches in Utrecht playing a particularly crucial role in their lives.

4.9. Organising and unionising of irregular migrant domestic workers

The FNV Migrant Domestic Workers Union is a grassroots organisation within the Dutch trade union federation FNV, formed and led by (irregular) migrant domestic workers themselves. Their logo is a fist in a yellow cleaning glove, clinching a large set of keys.

In 2008, domestic workers in the Netherlands organised themselves with the support of their communities and civil society organisations. The union started in light of the potential ratification of convention 189 of the International Labour Organisation. As mentioned before, the Netherlands has not ratified ILO189.

The migrant domestic workers union joined the FNV (Dutch Trade Union Confederation). Initially, their often undocumented status caused some hesitation within the union; their membership was accepted based on the principle that everyone who performs labour has the right to representation and protection. Since then, they have formed an active branch within the FNV, fighting for the recognition of domestic work as legitimate and valuable labour (FNV 2023). Today, the movement is primarily sustained mainly by the Indonesian and Filipino community organisations.

Established in response to the continuation of precarious and often invisible labour conditions faced by undocumented migrant domestic workers in the Netherlands, the union has two main objectives: firstly, the ratification of ILO Convention 189, which recognises domestic work as work, and the subsequent recognition of labour rights. Secondly, there is a need to regularise the status of irregular migrant workers. Next to this, they have intermediate goals and campaigns, such as their campaign for holiday pay (*vakantiegeld*), access to bank accounts, and the city ID for irregular migrants. Moreover, they offer Dutch lessons for domestic workers via the union. Next to this, they have the Migrant Domestic Workers Theatre Group, which, through art and theatre performances, seeks to create awareness about the struggles that irregular migrant domestic workers face.

5. Conclusion

This study sheds light on how irregularity impacts the daily lives of migrant domestic workers in Utrecht, exposing the intricate relationship between legal exclusion from the labour market, informal work arrangements, and community-based strategies. The Dutch domestic work sector is one of the most informal sectors in the Dutch labour market. Therefore, it presents an opportunity for irregular migrants to find employment. While the Dutch policy regulating domestic work, *Regeling Dienstverlening aan Huis*, provides rights to domestic workers, including those who are irregular, this is largely unknown to employers. Studies find that only 3% of employers follow the rules. The impact of irregular status, consequently, is primarily evident in the negotiation of working conditions, as it restricts domestic workers' ability to

advocate for their rights. The entrenched notion of "no work, no pay" prevails, leaving workers vulnerable to unexpected income loss due to illness, cancellations, or interpersonal conflicts. Attempts to improve working conditions, like union campaigns, can lead to termination. Still, some workers, especially those with strong local ties or entrepreneurial spirit, manage to navigate their work arrangements with more agency.

The dynamics of the domestic work relationship present a contradiction, as trust exists despite the absence of physical presence. Many domestic workers seldom interact with their employers yet gain access to the most personal corners of the home, holding keys and managing tasks that influence the intimate rhythms of everyday life. This trust typically stems not from personal relationships but from referrals and reputation. When employers are around, the dynamics can shift to be more personal and supportive, but it may blur professional lines and complicate discussions around pay and workload.

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